

METHODOLOGY OF USING EXERCISES TO BE PERFORMED AFTER THE TEXT IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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This article is dedicated to the methodology of using exercises performed after the texts in learning a foreign language, which exercises should be performed after the text for language learning and the importance of these exercises in language learning. It was recommended that exercises should be used to understand the content of the read text that the student's understanding should be checked after reading and understanding the text, that checking exercises should be given before reading the text and should be performed after reading.

This article is important for foreign language teachers in the process of language teaching, and for students studying foreign languages in the preparation of graduation papers.

Key words: *reading the text, the test exercises before reading the text, the test exercises after reading the text, preparatory exercises, speech exercises, the form of language materials, exercises based on specially prepared resources, exercises based on observation and ready-made sources*

As we know from the foreign language teaching methodology, exercises are used to understand the content of the read text. Students are given 2 types of exercises:

- 1) texts to develop information acquisition skills;
- 2) to understand the general content of the text.

After the student has read and understood the text, it is necessary to check the understanding. It is advisable to give the test exercises before reading the text, and then do it.

Before reading the text, the following exercises should be given and done after reading.

1. Answer the given questions.
2. Find the main points in the text, sentences and arguments.
3. The teacher gives the beginning of the sentence, and then the students find and read.
4. Find and read the sentence with the given word and translate it.
5. Speak the text content in English.

Exercises to be given and performed after reading the text:

1. Explain the content of the text in English.
2. Answer the questions.
3. Find a sentence that supports the teacher's point.
4. Find the speech situation in the text.
5. Add a title to the text.
6. Translate the given sentences or passages.

These exercises help students to develop their speaking skills while checking the content of the text. The main purpose of speaking the content of the text is to check the understanding of the content and to teach speaking.

The teacher chooses one of these exercises depending on the student's ability to check whether the students have understood the content of the text and to develop oral speech.

To teach speaking, it is necessary to perform a system of exercises aimed at a certain goal. It is common to divide such exercises into two groups:

1. Preparatory exercises.
2. Speech exercises.

Preparatory exercises prepare the foundation for speaking. With the help of such exercises, the student learns language material, acquires the skills of using it fluently in speech.

Examples of them are exercises such as: a) repetition of the language material without partially changing its form and b) with a partial change of the form of the language material (for example, substitution tables).

1. Logically changing the structure of the language material (replacing the position or form of sentence fragments, replacing senten-

ce fragments with other sentence fragments, replacing sentence fragments with synonyms or homonyms, etc.).

2. The form of language materials a) based on a sample; b) unsampled revision.
3. Language materials can be organized in 2 ways: 1) exercises based on specially prepared resources; 2) exercises based on observation and ready-made sources.

Exercises can be divided into three groups based on specially prepared resources.

1. Relying on formal signs (keywords, plan, title, etc.).
2. Relying on information sources (pictures, drawings, films and slides, text, etc.).
3. Relying on the mastered topic.

Observational and experiential exercises are also of two types:

1. Telling a story in the mother tongue based on information sources, telling a story by watching a silent film based on a picture, drawing, etc.
2. Based on the student's life experience (previously seen or read, own thoughts, imagination, etc.).

S. Saidaliev cited examples of these exercises in his work. Examples of exercises based on specially prepared resources are the following:

- repeating semantically related sentences (beginning, ending, person, tense) by changing them;
- creating a story based on key words, plan, given topic, given content in native language, etc.;
- description of pictures, picture system;
- interpretation of titles in a foreign language;
- determining and briefly justifying the topic of the radio broadcast, lecture, news, information of the listened story;
- identifying the sentences expressing the main meaning in the information and giving a title to the information;
- narrating the content of the text (summarizing and approximating the content of the text);
- shorten the heard message or the read text and express it using a few sentences;

- making a plan for the listened story;
- to describe the content of the text related to speech.

Examples of exercises that teach speaking:

- put a title and justify it;
- describe a picture that is not related to the studied topic;
- creating a story similar to the previously listened or read text;
- expressing one's attitude to things, events or reality;
- description of event or event participants, place or time;
- creating a short text (announcement, message, information, congratulation, etc.).

Examples of exercises that teach conversational speech:

- answering questions (briefly, fully, in detail);
- asking a question similar to the speech situation;
- converting listened or read speech into spoken speech;
- creating a conversation text on the given topic;
- conversation based on the text of the speech;
- change the content of the text about talking;
- answering questions thoroughly;
- conducting a complex topic, conversation, using expressions specific to the language being studied;
- conducting a discussion on the given topic.

The exercises listed above must meet the following requirements:

1. In terms of size, language complexity, condition, it should be suitable for students' strength.
2. Follow the principle of gradually increasing difficulties.
3. Be focused on a specific goal.
4. Increasing students' interest in language learning.
5. Acceleration of students' activities.
6. Structure based on vital and widespread speech situations.
7. Increasing the creative activity of students.
8. It should serve to develop the psychological characteristics of students (attention, anticipation, memory, and thinking).

Exercises are used to understand the content of the read text. Exercises are given to students in two ways:

1. To develop the skills of obtaining information from the text;

2. To understand the general content of the text.

After the student has read and understood the text, it is necessary to check the understanding. Review exercises should be given before reading the text and completed after reading.

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